

Ultra-High-Performance Concrete with Local Materials as Overlay Reinforcement of Slab Structural

Mardiana Oesman¹, Sintia Aulia², Yulianti³

^{1,2,3}Department of Civil Engineering, Politeknik Negeri Bandung, Jl. Gegerkalong Hilir, Ciwaruga, Kec. Parongpong, Kabupaten Bandung Barat, Jawa Barat 40559, INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

This research is an initial study on the strengthening of the existing normal reinforced concrete slab structure with Ultra-High-Performance-Concrete (UHPC) overlay using local materials without nano materials. The study began with the production of a UHPC mixture referring to a previous researcher, Meng (2017), with the type of SCM as a research variable. The cement used was OPC I, with the composition of SCM: silica fume content of 10%, 15%, and 20% with a fixed fly ash content of 15%. The maximum size used is the aggregate that passes the 4.75 mm sieve, is a combination of crushed stone (55%) and natural sand (45%). The ratio of water binder, w/b used is 0.22, superplasticizer content is 1% of the total weight of cementitious materials, and steel fiber content is 2% of the volume of concrete. Tests were carried out on the mechanical properties of UHPC. The results of the highest compressive test of the UHPC mixture, applied as an overlay on normal reinforced concrete slabs, became a hybrid composite structural element, which was then tested under flexural loads using the third point method. In addition to hybrid composite panels, a normal reinforcement concrete slabs were also made as a control specimen. The dimensions of the test specimens for the hybrid composite plate are 1000 mm x 400 mm x 60 mm and the thickness of the UHPC overlay is 20 mm thick. The test results show that the highest compressive strength of concrete was achieved by the mixture with the composition of SCM: 15% silica fume and 15% fly ash, which is 74.13 MPa at the age of 7 days; and at the age of 28 days obtained 65.17 MPa; thus, lower than the compressive strength of UHPC in general. However, the application of the highest performance concrete mix as overlays reinforcement for normal reinforced concrete slab has quite an effect on the hybrid composite slab. With the overlay, there is an increase in the flexural load capacity and ductility of the slab structure by 71%, and 166.22%, respectively. In addition, there is a difference in the stiffness behavior of the slab structure, in normal reinforced concrete structures, the stiffness would decrease after the first crack appears; however, in this hybrid composite structure, the stiffness will increase after the crack appears. The hybrid composite slab's crack pattern propagation behavior is also improved and distinct.

Corresponding Author:
Mardiana Oesman

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I. INTRODUCTION

Utilizing UHPC (Ultra High Performance Concrete) layers, major advancements in structural element repair and retrofit have been made. The UHPC layer's addition of dimensions does not add more to the reinforcement than does the concrete jacketing's addition of dimensions. This is due to the uniformly distributed steel fibers in UHPC, which apply tensile stress to the concrete and give it a high level of ductility even in the absence of reinforcement.

Compared to traditional concrete, UHPC is a new generation of concrete material with outstanding quality and durability. In general, UHPC is highly durable and has a compressive strength of 150 MPa [1,2,5,8,11,13, 14]. The extremely high compressive strength value is a result of the choice of constituent materials' low porosity value and high packing density of the particles [1,2,3,9,10,11,12,13,14].

A material with a fine grain size that reduces voids in the UHPC matrix is the UHPC constituent material that contributes to the low porosity value [5]. UHPC is often

created utilizing Nano-tech materials with aggregate sizes no larger than 0.8 mm [2, 11]. The voids in the concrete matrix will be filled by the fine grain size gradation, resulting in concrete with a high packing density [2,4,5,6,7]. The commercial cost of UHPC is high due to the usage of nano materials, which are not mass-produced. Due to the availability of supplies, strict quality control, and the high cost of UHPC constituent materials, the commercial pricing of UHPC is 20 times more expensive than regular concrete in the United States [3]. Additionally, the porosity value can be decreased by using a low w/b (water binding ratio) [4, 10, 11, 13]. In the UHPC mixture, industrial waste is used to partially replace cement as a concrete ingredient. Fly ash, ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBS), and silica fume are the most common SCM (Supplementary Cementing Materials) utilized in UHPC. Without significantly altering the mechanical qualities, partial cement replacement with SCM is possible [4]. It is advised to utilize cement with fine particles and have a minimum C3A or Tricalcium Aluminate content of 8% in UHPC mixtures [2]. This kind of cement is present in type III cement that has less C3A, although Indonesia does not make this kind of cement. Therefore, type I OPC was employed in this study. In addition, a superplasticizer was utilized to enhance the concrete mixture's workability due to the usage of water with a low w/b ratio of 0.14 to 0.22 [2]. In order to increase ductility and make UHPC strong enough to bear tensile and flexural forces without the addition of reinforcement, steel fibers ranging from 2 to 6 percent of the volume of concrete are used.

This study aims to obtain a mixture of UHPC proportions using local materials in order to keep manufacturing costs as low as possible because the recommended proportion of UHPC mixture is difficult to obtain in Indonesia. This study's goal was to ascertain how the UHPC overlay reinforced slab construction composed of local materials behaved. The first step in the research is to conduct a study to determine the UHPC mixture's composition. The composition of SCM serves as the study's variable. The UHPC design and mixing procedure was applied in accordance with earlier studies [4] that were altered in accordance with the tools available. The UHPC mixtures with the highest compressive strength will be used as an overlay reinforcement for reinforced concrete slab structures.

II. METHODOLOGY

Cement, fly ash, silica fume, natural sand, and crushed stone were the materials employed in this research, and assessing their qualities was the first step. Aggregates having a maximum size that could pass through a 4.75 mm sieve were used in this study. Since aggregate is made up of both natural sand and crushed stone, it is required to mix the two. In combining the aggregates, past research Meng (2017) was used as a guide.

The design of the UHPC mixture was carried out referring to Meng [4] with the composition of SCM as the research

variable. The SCM used was type F fly ash (15%) and silica fume (10%, 15%, 20%). Meanwhile, the w/b value is 0.22, and the steel fiber ratio is 2.5% of the concrete volume, and the superplasticizer is 1% of the total weight of cementitious materials.

A Hobart type mixer with a 12liter capacity is used to mix concrete. Cementitious ingredients are first manually blended, followed by 2 minutes of combining aggregate with cementitious materials in a mixer. The required water is then combined with a superplasticizer at a ratio of 90%, added to a mixer, and swirled for 4 minutes until it becomes a paste. The speed of the mixer is then raised. After that, manual stirring was done for two minutes to finish the mixture (break the dry mixture) and make it uniform with the previous mixture. The mixture is then mixed for 4 minutes to achieve homogeneity before the remaining water and steel fibers are added, and the mixer speed is increased for 1 minute. In accordance with ASTM C1611/C1611 M, the workability value of concrete was also evaluated in order to test its physical qualities. It was cured by submerging it in a water bath for the required amount of time, which was 7 days, 28 days, and 56 days before the test.

Then, the mechanical properties of UHPC were tested: compressive strength, splitting test, and flexural strength. The mixture with the highest compressive test results was applied to the hybrid composite slab test object, namely normal reinforced concrete slab reinforced with UHPC overlay. The plate test object consists of 2 test objects. The first test object is a normal reinforced concrete slab with dimensions of 1000 mm x 400 mm x 60 mm, as a control test object. The second test object is a hybrid composite slab consisting of 2 (two) layers with different types of concrete. The first layer is normal reinforced concrete with a thickness of 60 mm which behaves as an existing slab structure, and the second layer is a 20 mm thick UHPC overlay layer. The plate test object of normal concrete slab overlay by UHPC is shown in Fig. 1. Plate testing is carried out on bending, third point loading, load control. During the test, the magnitude of the load, the deflection that occurs, as well as the propagation of the crack pattern are observed. Deflection is measured at mid-span with a dial gauge.

Fig.1: Normal concrete slab overlay by UHPC (hybrid composite slab)

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The test results on the material properties show that the density of OPC cement obtained is 3.08, which meets the requirements of SNI 15-2049-2004, which is more than 3.0.

And, the fineness value (Blaine) of OPC cement is 402.35 m²/kg, fulfilling the minimum fineness value for all types of portland cement of 280 m²/kg, and higher than the results of the cement fineness test on the UHPC mixture conducted by Chen, et al, (2020) of 340 m²/kg. The test results on fly ash and silica fume are listed in Table 1. Meanwhile, the test results on the specific gravity of crushed stone is 2.63, slightly smaller than the test results of Meng, et al. (2017) which is 2.65. Meanwhile, the water absorption value in this study was 3.99%, much higher than the results of the Meng et al (2017) test, which was 0.14.

Fig 2: Aggregate combination grading curve

Table 1: Characteristic of SCM

	Standard	SCM		
		Cement	Fly Ash	Silica Fume
Specific Gravity	SNI 2531-2015	3,08	2,46	2,14
Blaine (m ² /kg)	ASTM C 204-00/SNI 15-2049-2004	402,35	512,81	-

The results of testing on sand are listed in Table 2, where the specific gravity reaches 2.5 lower than the test results of Meng, et al. (2017), which is 2.64. And the water absorption value is known to be 6.24%, much higher than the Meng test results that is 0.06%. In general, to achieve high concrete quality, a specific gravity of sand and gravel above 2.6 is used. However, in this study used sand that is available in the local market with a lower density of sand. Likewise, the water absorption of the aggregate used in this study is quite high, so the w/b used will be higher than the w/b used in UHPC in general.

Table 2: Characteristic of aggregates

	Standard	Crushed stone	Sand
		SSD Specific Gravity	SNI 1969-2008/SNI 1970-2008
Water absorption (%)	SNI 1969-2008/SNI 1970-2008	3,99	6,24
Sludge level (%)	SNI 03-4142-1996	4,92	4,06

In this study, the aggregate gradation refers to the aggregate gradation curve of Meng et al.; So, it must be mixed between crushed stone and sand. To achieve the gradation curve, the percentage of sand and crushed stone combined is 45% and 55%, respectively. Thus, the UHPC mixed aggregate gradation curve is obtained as shown in Fig.2.

In this study, the composition of SCM is variable. The SCM used were fly ash and silica fume. The fly ash content remained at 15%, while the silica fume content was different. As shown in Table 3, there are 3 mixtures of UHPC.

Table 3: SCM content in UHPC mixture

Sample Code	Fly Ash	Silica Fume
S10F15	15 %	10 %
S15F15	15 %	15 %
S20F15	15 %	20 %

Table 4 is the composition of three UHPC mixtures and normal concrete mixture. The UHPC mixtures were designed with the w/b value is 0.22, and the steel fiber ratio is 2.5% of the concrete volume, and the superplasticizer is 1% of the total weight of cementitious materials. Normal concrete is designed with a compressive strength of 20 MPa.

Table 4: Concrete mixtures

	Unit	UHPC Mixtures			Normal Concrete Mixture
		S10F15	S15F15	S20F15	
Cement	kg/m ³	804	750,40	696.8	357.407
Sand	kg/m ³	454.95	454,95	454.95	778.519
Crushed stone	kg/m ³	556.05	556.05	556.05	939.192
Silica fume	kg/m ³	107.2	160,80	214.40	-
Fly ash	kg/m ³	160.8	160,80	160.80	-
Superplasticizer	kg/m ³	10.72	10.72	10.72	-
Steel fiber	kg/m ³	156	156	156	-
Water	kg/m ³	225.12	225,12	225.12	186.443
binder (Cement + Silica fume + Fly ash)	kg/m ³	1072	1072	1072	
w (superplasticizer + water)	kg/m ³	235.84	235.84	235.84	-
w/b		0.22	0.22	0.22	-

Fresh concrete testing was carried out with slump flow with a flow time of 10 seconds. The slump flow results, as shown in Table 5, are in the range of the results of the previous

UHPC study, Manoj et al. that is between 600 mm – 800mm.

Table 5: Slump Flow Test

Sample Code	Slump Flow (mm)
S10F15	685
S15F15	685
S20F15	650

Table 6 and Fig.3 show the results of the compressive strength testing of concrete from three different mixture compositions. The data shows that the highest average compressive strength was achieved by the mixture of S15F15 at the age of 7 days and 28 days, which was 74.13 MPa and 65.17 MPa. And, the highest average compressive strength at the age of 56 days was achieved by a mixture of S20F15, 70.23 MPa. The results of this test indicate that the highest compressive strength is achieved at the age of 7 days. For mixtures with 10% and 15% silica fume composition, the compressive strength tends to decrease at the age of 56 days, but this behavior is reversed in the mixture with 20% silica fume composition. Overall, the results of the compressive strength test show that the highest compressive strength is lower than the general compressive strength of UHPC, which is above 100 MPa. This is due, among other things, poor local material properties, the mixing method used, and the very simple curing method. Based on the achieved compressive strength, this concrete is equivalent to high performance concrete with a minimum compressive strength of 41.4 MPa based on SNI 03-6468-2000.

Table 6: Compressive strength

No	Sample Code	Loads (kN)			Compressive Strength (MPa)		
		7 days	28 days	56 days	7 days	28 days	56 days
1.	S10F15	493.	589.	471.	62.4	75.2	60.3
	-1	00	40	40	5	4	0
2.	S10F15	519.	465.	345.	66.4	599	42.6
	-2	90	00	30	1	8	2
3.	S10F15	403.	398.	2681	51.2	50.8	34.7
	-3	20	40	0	1	4	0
Average Compressive Strength					60.0	62.0	45.8
					2	2	7
1.	S15F15	618.	534.	348.	79.4	67.9	44.6
	-1	30	40	60	2	9	4
2.	S15F15	615.	624.	279.	78.3	76.5	36.5
	-2	60	90	50	2	4	5
3.	S15F15	517.	404.	460.	64.6	50.9	56.5
	-3	80	50	90	5	9	0
Average Compressive Strength					74.1	65.1	45.9
					3	7	0
1.	S20F15	399.	460.	549.	50.2	57.9	71.2

	-1	90	80	70	8	5	0
2.	S20F15	474.	366.	473.	60.8	46.7	60.4
	-2	80	30	10	1	0	8
3.	S20F15	460.	507.	632.	57.8	65.8	79.0
	-3	30	30	30	0	6	1
Average Compressive Strength					56.1	56.8	70.2
					3	4	3

Fig.3: Compressive strength concrete

Table 7 and Fig. 4 show the results of the splitting strength test of 3 concrete mix compositions. The test results showed that at the age of 28 days and 56 days, the highest value was achieved by a mixture of S15F15, which was 11.11 MPa and 16.10 MPa, respectively. This value is almost the same as the test results of Meng, et al. (2017) at the age of 28 days of concrete is 11.6 MPa.

Table 7: Splitting tensile strength

Sample Code	Flexural Strength (MPa)		
	7 days	28 days	56 days
S10F15	7.57	8.01	11.96
S15F15	11.11	8.56	16.10
S20F15	8.23	11.58	12.85

Fig. 4: Splitting strength of concrete

Table 8 and Fig.5 show the results of the flexural strength testing of concrete from three different mixture compositions. The data shows that the highest flexural strength was achieved by the mixture of S10F15 at the age of 7 days, which was 16.73 MPa. And, the highest flexural strength at the age of 56 days was achieved by a mixture of S15F15, which was 14.36 MPa.

Table 8: Flexural strength

No	Sample Code	Flexural Strength (MPa)		
		7 days	28 days	56 days
1.	S10F15	16.73	10.36	13.91
2.	S15F15	10.01	9.28	14.36
3.	S20F15	10.98	12.12	11.17

Fig. 4: Flexural strength of concrete

Furthermore, based on the results of the compressive strength testing of the 3 types of UHPC mixtures, the mixture with the highest compressive strength was applied as overlay reinforcement for normal reinforced concrete slab. However, to determine the effect of the UHPC overlay, a normal reinforced concrete slab was tested as a control test object. The test results on the control test objects are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. The first crack vertically occurs in the tension zone in the mid-span, which is a flexural crack. However, further crack propagation until failure occurs, forming exactly at the load point, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig 5: Crack pattern of normal concrete slab

The test results of normal reinforced concrete slabs (as control specimen) under flexural loading are shown in Fig.6. The figure shows a graph of the relationship between the load and the deflection at the center of the span. The maximum load achieved is 7.6 kN with a deflection of 5.6 mm. Immediately after the first crack occurs, the stiffness of the structure decreases, the second modulus, EI^{nd} is smaller than the first modulus, EI^{st} , this behavior is common in reinforced concrete structural elements when loaded under flexural load. Yield load is achieved when $P_y = 7.5$ kN and deflection $\delta_y = 0.73$ mm. Meanwhile, the ultimate load is achieved when $P_u = 7.6$ kN and the deflection, $\delta_u = 5.6$ mm. Thus the value of ductility that occurs is = 7.4.

Fig. 6: Load vs deflection graph of reinforced normal concrete slabs

Next, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the test results on hybrid composite slabs, namely normal reinforced concrete slabs reinforced with UHPC overlays. Fig.7 shows crack pattern of composite hybrid composite slab. The first crack occurs when the vertical linear graph changes to a horizontal graph, when the load reaches 12 kN. After the first crack, loading continues until the next cracks propagate from the normal concrete layer to the top surface (interface) of normal concrete with the bottom surface of the UHPC overlay. When delamination occurs at the interface, along with the occurrence of horizontal crack propagation in the UHPC layer which ends the failure process.

Fig 7: Crack pattern of normal concrete slab

The figure 8 shows a graph of the relationship between the load and the deflection at the center of the span. The maximum load achieved is 13 kN with a deflection of 26 mm. Immediately after the first crack occurs, the stiffness of the structure increases, EI^{nd} is greater than EI^{st} , and EI^{rd} is also greater than EI^{nd} ; This behavior is inversely related to the behavior of reinforced concrete structural elements when loaded under bending. Yield load is achieved when $P_y = 12$ kN and deflection $\delta_y = 1.32$ mm. Meanwhile, the ultimate load is achieved when $P_u = 13$ kN and the deflection, $\delta_u = 26$ mm. Thus, the ductility value that occurs is = 19.27. Thus, with the presence of a 20mm thick UHPC overlay on a normal reinforced concrete slab, there was an increase in load capacity and ductility of 71%, and 166.22%, respectively, these differences as shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 8: Load vs deflection graph of hybrid composite slabs

Fig. 9: Load vs deflection graph of slabs

IV. CONCLUSION

The design of the concrete mix is strongly influenced by the properties of the constituent material, it cannot only depend on the composition of the forming mixture and the gradation of the aggregate size, as well as its w/w. The results of testing on the mechanical properties of 3 concrete mixtures using local materials, with aggregate passing through a 4.75mm sieve, fly ash and sika fume as SCM, OPC cement 1, steel fiber 2.5%, at w/w 0.22 shows the highest compressive strength of concrete achieved by the mixture with the composition of SCM: 15% sika fume and 15% fly ash, which is 74.13 MPa at the age of 7 days. Thus, lower than the compressive strength of UHPC in general.

However, the application of the highest quality concrete mix as overlays reinforcement for normal reinforced concrete slab has quite an effect on the hybrid composite slab. With the overlay, there is an increase in the flexural load capacity and ductility of the slab structure by 71%, and 166.22%, respectively. In addition, there is a difference in the stiffness behavior of the slab structure, in normal reinforced concrete structures, the stiffness would decrease after the first crack appears; however, in this hybrid composite structure, the stiffness will increase after the crack appears. The hybrid composite slab's crack pattern propagation behavior is also improved and distinct.

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